

Isochrone Overlapping: A Novel Approach to Mobility and Infrastructure Planning

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Abstract—In this article we propose a novel approach for mobility analysis by isochrone overlapping to aid urban planners in the decision-making processes of walkable cities for all citizens. This approach focuses on the pedestrian mobility of older citizens but can accommodate different accessibility requirements to quantify the mobility of users. As will be seen, the proposed approach offers great insight for the X-minute city concept and chronourbanism as it unveils new data exploitation that enhances spatially aware analysis and optimization. The reduction in computation complexity of simulation has been quantified and tested. A streamlined workflow is proposed for the evaluation of indicators related to accessible walking and also the identification of the best locations for new services.

I. INTRODUCTION

The passage of time is a phenomenon that binds all people to the same reality and we are slowly walking towards an aged society that will present unprecedented challenges, as studies have identified [1]. Challenges like the growing concern about the economic strain that the ever-increasing life expectancy will put on care services. But an often overlooked fact is that even if we were to solve that challenge, we could eventually still find our older selves in a urban landscape that is not accessible anymore for our new walking needs. Currently, this is both a future possibility and a present reality for many citizens.

Regarding this concern, accessibility in the city is an important topic, since being able to reach daily amenities is key to a successful aging [2]–[4]. Furthermore, events like the COVID-19 pandemic has amplified the mental health toll that social isolation and confinement can entail [5]. An untraversable urban graph can contribute to the isolation of older citizens and routing algorithms solutions are not particularly designed to account for mobility-restricted needs.

The challenges defined above are currently being addressed from many perspectives. This work contributes to the existing tools and methodologies available for urban planners supporting their efforts to create more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient urban environments by presenting a method that can cater for on of the most secluded groups in the streets, our seniors.

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This is a presubmission version of the paper and it contains mistakes. For the official version seek the published paper

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A. Related work

To address urban design challenges like the walkability of streets, many urbanism concepts have been gaining popularity lately. *Chronourbanism*, for example, is a philosophy that focuses on the time it takes to traverse the urban network by car or walking [6]. Derived from *Chronourbanism* the *x-minute city* concept can be found. *x-minute city* is being promoted throughout the world and focuses on the ability of any citizen to reach their daily locations in less than x minutes which is usually 15 minutes [7], [8]. This concept can help defining cities that cater for accessible pedestrian transit as the main mobility system, diverging from the dependency of cars and improving upon the many social, health and independence benefits that walking offers. Currently, European citizens are at around 3 and 7 km away from daily amenities [9], which is 40 minutes away from the *15-minute city* in the best case given older citizens walking speed.

Urban planners have been using isochrone maps to address mobility at least since 1881 when Francis Galton published his *Proceedings of the Royal Geographical Society*. This polygon shaped data describe the area you can get to given an origin point and a traversing configuration. Usually, the traversing configuration is merely an average speed and restrictions of what you can and cannot cross. Some of the most common example that can be found in the literature are public or private automobile transportation analysis that don not provide municipality level suggestions [9], or the definition of the *Functional Urban Area* that goes beyond the administrative boundaries of the cities [10].

However, similar to routing algorithm solutions used to evaluate amenity proximity, isochrone analyses are not often designed to accommodate pedestrian accessibility-restricted citizens. Proposed algorithms that can be found in the literature assume unimpeded walking configuration which are not suitable for older citizens [11]–[14] or are either focus on traffic [15] or public transport [16].

Some walking studies can be found that are focused on older citizens walking conditions such as the Age-Friendly Route Planner [17] and developed within *URBANAGE*.

Isochrone analysis is described in [18] as a fast approach to evaluate the x-minute city, but it lacks the ability to evaluate accessibility and equity opportunities. However, to the best of our knowledge, using aggregations of isochrone maps has never been used as a way to define urban mobility and assess these accessibility or equity opportunities. In this study an aggregated isochrone map approach is presented to describe

accessibility requirements.

This work follows previously developed tools and studies within the project of *URBANAGE*¹, an European initiative focused on helping urban planners and policy makers harness the power of new technologies for more inclusive, evidence based decisions. Specifically this study uses the *Age Friendly Route Planner (AFRP)* as it can provide accessible routing solutions [17]. Also an index that evaluates the friendliness of the urban environment for older adults named *Age Friendly Neighborhood Index (AFNI)* is used [19]. This index combines multiple indicators that were identified from cocreation methodologies in *URBANAGE* [20], [21]. Indicators related to accessibility are, for example, access to convenience stores, open spaces, community centers, worship or cultural facilities. Regarding modelization that include older citizens pedestrian walking [7]. Lastly, in relation to the accessibility for older citizens, an optimization study on conveying infrastructure placement has been developed [22].

Some studies regarding older citizens outside of *URBANAGE* are a study on private car mobility for older citizens [23] and an analysis of "what do older persons perceive as barriers to using fixed-route public transit [24].

B. Contribution

With all this, the main contribution of this work can be divided into two separate but complementary isochrone aspects:

- A fast approach to measure and evaluate *walkability related indicators*² with accessibility requirements.
- A novel approach to mobility analysis based on isochrone overlapping maps that can help find the best locations to build infrastructure and quantify its effect on *walkability related indicators*².

The rest of this manuscript is organized as follows: in the following Section II, the methods implemented in our research are described. In Section III, the conducted experimentation is detailed, analyzing also the results obtained. This work finishes in Section IV introducing the main conclusions and further work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to provide solutions that can better resemble older citizens and those with specific accessibility requirements the *Age Friendly Route Planner (AFRP)* is used [17]. These routing algorithm can describe the target group of this study and its walking configuration that is described in the following Subsection II-A.

The challenge introduced in this work will be tested in Santander. This northern Spanish city has a steep orography that can make streets untraversable for older adults. Urban planners in Santander City Council have developed urban infrastructure aimed to improve walkability.

¹<https://www.urbanage.eu/>

²In the use case presented in this study walking related indicators require specific services to be within reach of the households.

Elevators, mechanical escalators and ramps are key enablers for older citizens accessibility.

Evaluating the reachability of all households to their daily amenities and the friendliness of the city is a combinatorially complex task. To address this issue, a study to reduce the complexity of this evaluation is presented in this paper. The data required for this use case is described in the following Subsection II-B and its preprocessing in Subsection II-C.

The work presented in this paper, based on isochrone analysis, is intended to aid urban planners in evaluating the friendliness of the city and suggest the best locations for new services that target isolated citizens in an efficient way. Proposed methods are described in Subsection II-D

A. Problem formulation

This study is focused on the walkability of older citizens and gathers the walking configuration that describes this group's accessibility requirements. First, a maximum walking speed of 0.9 m/s has been defined as this speed is the slowest speed for an older citizen in dry condition [7]. A maximum slopes of 8° is set as higher steepness reduces pedestrian security for older adults [25]. Considering wheelchair accessibility, and older citizens reluctance of taking stairs and mechanical escalators, both have been defined as inaccessible. Additionally, a time constrain has been defined to establish the reachability of amenities. This time constrain is set to 10 minutes as it is the smallest time given to the *x-minute city* concept. This combination sets a maximum walking distance of 540 meters but conveying ramps and elevators will not add up to the walked distance. All parameters have been approved by Santander civil servants as representative for older citizens.

It is noteworthy that all these parameters can be customized to better assess a particular use case. Which is even more interesting is that different walking configurations could be combined to evaluate particular citizen patterns. Optional configurations could be to avoid elevators for claustrophobic people or women in night-shifts, or a different time constraint and faster average speeds.

Lastly, in order to evaluate the age friendliness of the city and quantify the improvement, two indicators that rely upon accessibility within the conditions mentioned above have been taken into account: the access to open spaces and the access to convenience stores. These indicators are based on the *AFNI* but they just serve a proof-of-concept purpose.

B. Required data

This is the data required for this study:

- *City_graph.osm*: the graph $G=(E, V)$ of the city in *osm* format. E is the amount of edges in the graph and V the amount of vertices. Downloadable here: <https://extract.bbbike.org/>
- *City_elevation.tiff*: Orography of the city so so routes can calculate slopes. Downloadable here: <https://dwtkns.com/srtm/>
- *City_neighborhoods.json*: digital boundaries of the administrative areas in *geojson* format with an id

property and other properties required for indicator calculation of such as population and area.

- `City_households.csv`: all the household addresses of the city geolocalized. H is the amount of households in the city.
- `Service_folder/services.csv`: all the services of the city, provided in geolocalized way. S_i is the amount of services of type i and all indicator add up to S .

C. Preprocessing

All geolocalized data is parsed to a specific predefined coordinate system as these files can be provided in completely unrelated coordinates systems. In this study we have chosen longitude-latitude values as this coordinate system is the one used in *OSM*. Also longitude-latitude coordinates work in any part of the world as opposed to *UTM* coordinates that rely on zones. Data that require parsing are city households, city neighborhoods delimitations and all services.

All city households coordinates are then tested within every neighborhood so a neighborhood-household relation can be established and neighborhood indicator can be evaluated. At the same time, all services are classified into their respective indicators. For example, supermarkets, grocery stores, and convenience stores are joined into one service as all of them represent the access to groceries. This final category is what will later be used to filter out households that are already satisfied by these services, and provide the isochrone overlapping technique with only the household polygons that are lacking said service categories.

D. Method

Isochrones represent the geographical area you can get to a given origin point, a time limit and a walking configuration. Previously, in the context of the *URBANAGE* project, a custom route planner was developed to better describe the traversing conditions of older citizens. This route planner can output isochrones that avoid unfriendly streets defined in Subsection II-A.

Requesting *OTP* an isochrone from each household address will return a polygon that represents the area defined by all the walking distances that can be traveled by an individual with a set of conditions (included travel speed) and who departs from the specific household address. The conditions that define the traveler can be modified for a particular scenario. Thus, affecting the distances the travelers can make and ultimately the definition of the isochrone polygon.

The isochrone polygon is used to evaluate the friendliness per household by checking which services are within reach of the household, or inside the said polygon, as Figure 1 shows. This way we avoid calculating routes from every household to every service.

This polygon is calculated by means of the *Dijkstra algorithm* [26] throughout the urban graph taking into account the walkability configuration previously described in Subsection II-A. Dijkstra has a $\mathcal{O}(V \log E/V)$ complexity

Fig. 1. A household in Santander with 10 Open space locations within accessible reach with older citizens mobility requirements. Icons by pixelbazaar.

and $\Theta(n^2)$ Big-Theta notation [27]. Meanwhile, the *A* algorithm* is the state-of-the-art route planning algorithm to route from an origin point to a destination point and has a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(b^d)$ and $\Theta(m \times n)$ Big-Theta notation [27], where $0 \leq m \leq n$. Even if Dijkstra is on average slower than *A**, as it does not prune edges, the isochrone calculation would only be required to be executed once per household address and then checked if services are within the polygon. The specific implementation for this function is the even-odd algorithm [28], and its complexity is described as $\mathcal{O}(V_{\text{polygon}})$ where V_{polygon} represents the amount of vertices in the polygon [29]. This reduces the complexity of the evaluation if services are within isochrones from $\Theta(H \times S \times m \times n)$ to $\Theta(H \times N^2 + S \times V_{\text{polygon}})$. Also, acquiring the isochrones geometrical shape offers a valuable mobility report to better understand the walking area of every household.

An optimized simulation process can be derived from this isochrone approach, and it emerges when previous simulation are already calculated. Isochrone recalculation is only required when the city graphs walkability changes, which occurs during the following conditions: *i*) the city graph has been modified (*osm* file); or *ii*) the pedestrian mobility has changed with new infrastructure being added (reducing said streets traversing cost to 0) or some being now untraversable (increasing said streets traversing cost to infinity). Although this feature has not yet been published, both things can be done in the *AFRP* by providing the new conveying or untraversable ways ids [17].

This optimized simulation process happens when: a simulation derives from a previously computed one, the city graph is not modified, and the pedestrian mobility has changed as in case *ii*. In such case, only the affected isochrones that are impacted by the modified street edges need to be recalculated. The rest of the isochrones will be unaffected by the new mobility infrastructure and can be simply loaded from disk. Consequently, concatenated simulation will experience a reduction in computation complexity improving time execution and streamlining optimization processes as described in II-D.1.

In order to evaluate the indicators of a city and also evaluate the isochrone overlapping maps, we introduce the workflow described in Figure 2 which is designed for isochrones and includes the steps in blue and the required data for each step to be executed in green.

Fig. 2. Proposed workflow of the isochrone overlapping approach for indicator evaluation and best suitable location information extraction.

This workflow is composed of the following steps:

1) *Setup*: The first step in this approach is to load all the information required for the mobility analysis. This information is the household addresses and the administrative delimitation: `City_household.json` and `City_neighborhoods.json`. Also, an instance of AFRP should be online which requires the city graph and the city elevation files: `City_graph.osm` and `City_elevation.tiff`. Then, isochrones maps are computed and stored for future simulations. The proposed algorithm for isochrone calculation is described in Algorithm II-D.1 with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(H)\mathcal{O}(E \times \log V)$.

Algorithm 1 Isochrone computation $\mathcal{O}(H) \times \mathcal{O}(E \times \log V)$

Input: H is geolocalized city household addresses. E and V are the amount of edges and vertices in the city graph respectively.

Output: Isochrone polygons per household address

Procedure:

```

isochrone_list ← initialize_list
for all  $loc \in H$  do                                ▷  $\mathcal{O}(H)$ 
     $isoc \leftarrow isoc\_Dijkstra(loc)$                 ▷  $\mathcal{O}(E \times \log V)$ 
     $isochrone\_list[i] \leftarrow isoc$ 
end for
return  $isochrone\_list$ 

```

If the simulations were previously computed, then stored simulations could be loaded from disk instead of computing them again. Alternatively, if the current simulation is not stored but it derives from previous simulation, such as case ii described in Section II, then only isochrones affected by the changes require recomputing. Possible changes between simulations include the construction of new mobility infrastructure or the declaration of streets as untraversable. Checking whether a new infrastructure or street is within a polygon can be verified with the algorithm proposed in Algorithm II-D.2 but instead of services one should provide

the street vertices. If one of the street vertices lies within the polygon then that isochrone is affected. This approach would reduce the time complexity resulting in $\mathcal{O}(h)\mathcal{O}(E \times \log V)$ where $0 \leq h \leq H$.

The result should contain not only the isochrone polygon as it is, but an ID that identifies each household univocally. This way, indicator calculations that rely in percentage of coverage of households can be quickly obtained.

2) *Count services within reach*: Once the setup is completed, every household H isochrone can be used to check how many services S each household can access to in accessibility conditions. In order to count the amount of services each services is checked if they lay within each household isochrone and then counted. The proposed algorithm for this evaluation is detailed in Algorithm II-D.2 and has a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(P \times S \times V_{poly})$. Some indicators might require the amount of services within the neighborhood, this can be achieved by providing the neighborhood polygons N to the algorithm instead of the household's isochrone polygons $\mathcal{O}(N \times S \times V_{poly})$.

Algorithm 2 Are points within polygon $\mathcal{O}(P \times S \times V_{poly})$

Input P is a list of polygons usually isochrones from households (H). S is a list of geolocalized services by their type. V_{poly} are the amount of vertices in each polygon.

Output Count how many services of different types are within polygons

Procedure:

```

for all  $i, poly \in P$  do                                ▷  $\mathcal{O}(P)$ 
    for all  $type, points \in S$  do                        ▷  $\mathcal{O}(S)$ 
         $inside \leftarrow is\_within(poly, points)$         ▷  $\mathcal{O}(V_{poly})$ 
         $serv\_count\_per\_poly[i, type] \leftarrow count(inside)$ 
    end for
end for
return  $serv\_count\_per\_poly$ 

```

3) *Evaluate indicators*: Multiple indicators can be evaluated once all the services within reach are counted for every household and neighborhood. The most relevant indicators for an analysis based on isochrone overlapping are those relying in computing Manhattan distances from the households to a certain service or amenity, for example: access to public open spaces, access to convenience stores or access to worship facilities... These indicators usually require a single accessible service but if multiple services shall be required then the threshold can be tested against the service count. The indicators are calculated as a percentage of household that have access to those services per neighborhood: $\frac{H_i^{fulfilling}}{H_i}$ where $H_i^{fulfilling}$ represents the amount of households of neighborhood i that fulfill the indicator. When these indicators are evaluated, the households that do not fulfill the minimum thresholds are identified as isolated.

The households that do not fulfill the indicators are a crucial part of the mobility analysis as they comprehend the target for urban solutions as they are not only the

ones that can improve the overall city index, but they might also represent isolated citizens if they indeed have reduced mobility. Additionally, as households are identified, age demographic information can be used to prioritize households with older citizens.

4) *Compute isochrone overlapping*: Lastly, after every household isochrone is calculated and after all isolated households are identified, then the isochrone overlapping technique can provide a great insight about the new urban solution locations. Isochrone overlapping is used to produce a heatmap that represents those isolated households and can also quantify the effect on the city friendliness index. The improvement a neighborhood would experience from the construction of a new service at a specific location can be measured by $H_i^{overlapped}$, which represents the number of isolated household isochrone maps that overlap in that location for neighborhood i . The total improvement across all neighborhoods can be calculated as $\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{H_i^{overlapped}}{H_i}$. If the service is built at that location, the isolated houses would gain access to it, thereby increasing the percentage of houses covered by services and improving the indicator.

After computing the whole set of isochrone maps for each household, their aggregation can be presented in the shape of a heatmap. The heatmap is projected over a grid with 6000x6000 dimensions. For each cell in the grid, the accumulated isochrone overlapping is computed and defines its color. Alternatively, the color could represent the improvement that the indicator provides for the city if the indicator weights are provided.

The isochrone overlapping algorithm proposed in this study is described in Algorithm II-D.4 with a time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(M \times P \times V_{poly})$ where M represents the grid's amount of points. By storing the household IDs in a matrix that represents the map, isochrone overlapping can be executed just once per simulation. This way the matrix would contain the reach of each household for the specific simulation. Then households can then be filtered out depending on what service is being analyzed. Furthermore, this process can be accelerated by checking the bounding box of each isochrone before computing the `is_within` function.

Algorithm 3 Isochrone overlapping $\mathcal{O}(M \times P \times V_{poly})$

Input: M is a matrix of geolocalized points, M_{IDs} is a matrix of lists of IDs, P is isochrone polygon list, V_{poly} is the amount of vertices in the isochrone polygons.

Output: Isochrone overlapping.

Procedure:

```

 $M_{IDs} \leftarrow$  initialize with size of  $M$ 
for all  $point \in M$  do  $\triangleright \mathcal{O}(M)$ 
  for all  $poly \in P$  do  $\triangleright \mathcal{O}(P)$ 
     $inside \leftarrow is\_within(poly, point)$   $\triangleright \mathcal{O}(V_{poly})$ 
     $M_{IDs}[inside] \leftarrow$  add isochrone ID
  end for
end for
return  $M_{IDs}$ 

```

Once the isochrone overlapping has been obtained and households that already have access to a particular services have been filtered out, the best place to build a new service where most of the household congregate can be located. Unfortunately, due to the density of the city's urban fabric in Santander, the global maximum will usually point to a location that is not suitable for a new intervention. Thus, in order to be more flexible, we propose defining a range of percentiles with the best places based on the household amount that overlap in each grid cell or the indicator improvement. Hereby, when classifying these grid cells based on the their percentile range we can find the contours shapes and output a polygon. These percentile polygons, and in particular the best percentiles, can be now visualize loosely defined areas that can help urban planner allocate new services catering reduce accessibility mobility conditions. Examples of an isochrone overlapping solutions in Santander can be seen in Subsection III-B.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The following two subsections will illustrate the benefits of the complementary isochrone approaches to provide urban planning solutions. First the complexity reduction of the isochrone approach will be put to the test. Then examples of the visual aid and the data that the isochrone overlapping technique provides will be showcase.

A. Testing services within reach

In this subsection, the efficiency of the two methods will be compared by evaluating their respective execution times. The first method involves routing from each origin point to each destination point through A* (point-to-point). This approach can be found in the literature [13]. The second one is the isochrone approach described in Section II-D.1 and Section II-D.2.

Previously, in Section II, the complexity of both approaches has been described in Big- \mathcal{O} and Big- Θ notation and the hypothesis is that isochrone maps will take less time to evaluate indicators as its complexity is smaller.

The experiment consists of two tests. The first test will involve determining the total amount of services that are within a walkable configuration from every household. The objective of the second test is to verify the presence of a single service accessible to each household, which should benefit the point-to-point method as it can break the loop and proceed to the next household.

The tests will be conducted with $N=13705$ households (all Santander) and $S=3939$ services (benches). It will be executed in Python 3.8 on a Windows 10 64bits with specs: Intel i7-11850H @ 2.50GHz and 32 GB of RAM.

First and second runs of both tests are distinguished as isochrone polygons can be calculated once, stored and loaded for subsequent evaluations. Isochrone recalculation will only be required when the graph changes. Particularly if a new conveying ramp or elevator is built or if a street is declared untraversable. If previous simulations are already

TABLE I
EXPERIMENT ON EXECUTION TIME

Method	Steps	Complexity		First time		Second time	
		Big- \mathcal{O} notation	Big- Θ notation	Test 1	Test 2	Test 1	Test 2
1	Household to each service	$\mathcal{O}(H \times S) \times \mathcal{O}(b^d)$	$\Theta(H \times S \times m \times n)$	158 hours	31 hours	158 hours	31 hours
2	Isochrone calculation Points within polygon	$\mathcal{O}(H) \times \mathcal{O}(E \times \log V)$ $\mathcal{O}(H \times S) \times \mathcal{O}(V_{\text{polygon}})$	$\Theta(H \times n^2)$ $\Theta(H \times S) \times \Theta(V_{\text{polygon}})$	1h 1m 23s 53s		1s 53s	

calculated, then, as described in Subsection II-D.1, only affected isochrones would require recomputing.

The test results are provided in Table I. As can be observed, the execution time of the second method surpasses the first in both tests. Comparing both methods, the isochrone approach has achieved a drop in execution time and it takes one thirtieth of the time it takes the first method to evaluate the second test. But, improvement is not only reflected in execution time. The isochrone approach will also provide more data as it counts the total amount of services. Lastly, it is worth noting that when more services have to be tested it will further emphasize the advantage of the isochrone method.

B. Scenario of best locations to build infrastructure by isochrone overlapping

In Figure 3 and Figure 4 we can see two example of an isochrone overlapping analysis that targets the best location to build *open spaces* and *convenience stores* taking into account the households that do not already have access to these services within accessible walkable configuration. We can also know how much a single service would improve the overall index if this was applied. Instead of indicator improvements what is showed is the amount of household that overlaps within that area. This is so it is easier to understand as indicators are weighted and their meaning gets obfuscated. The four colors represent the quartiles of the improvement when building a service within that polygon. The yellow polygons (first quartile) is the best areas to place a service, as in those areas the service would be granted to the largest amount of households possible. Orange, red and gray areas represent the remaining quartiles.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work has presented two complementary methods for improving the way in which urban mobility for senior citizens is designed. On one hand, a fast indicator calculation for routing related indicators. A method that streamlines both the index evaluations and simulations of cities. On the other hand, a novel approach for urban mobility analytics based on the superposition of isochrone maps, which is intended to help urban planners find the best location for new service construction and quantify the improvement.

As experiments suggest, isochrone maps are a faster approach to evaluate indicators by dropping the simulation run time in Santander use case to one thirtieth of the time required with the currently existing method as described in

Fig. 3. Isochrone overlapping of households without access to open spaces in older citizens walking conditions. Colored polygons indicate the best locations to build new open access locations. Icons by pixelbazaar.

Fig. 4. Isochrone overlapping of households without access to convenience stores in older citizens walking conditions. Colored polygons indicate the best locations to build new convenience stores. Icons by pixelbazaar.

Subsection III-A. This increased performance, enables the system to perform more complex simulations:

- Evaluation of the effect of new service construction in minutes.
- Evaluation of the effect of incidents (untraversable routes) and new mobility infrastructure (elevator, ramps) built in the city graph in a thirtieth of the time it would take by routing.

We have also presented a workflow and the algorithms required for *Isochrone Overlapping*, their time complexity and some tips to improve the performance of consecutive simulations. In the light of the results, we believe

that this approach paves the way for spatially aware optimization and can potentially combine different scenarios based on their walking configurations. Also a multi-factor isochrone overlapping could be achieved by weighting different isochrone overlapping maps based on the current urban needs. These analysis could target households with: accessibility requirements, older citizens, night-shift woman workers that will avoid elevators, badly insulated houses for heatwaves that need a climate shelter and so on...

As for now isochrone overlapping has been tested for service location placement to improve accessibility of households and thus it has followed a biased towards higher density areas. But evenly distributed isochrone maps could describe the overall city graph's accessibility and help evaluate the best locations for urban accessibility infrastructure.

As a concluding remark, the proposed methodology could enhance the way in which senior citizen mobility is managed. This approach could potentially help analyze scenarios that will make urban environments sustainable, inclusive, and resilient.

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